

Hospital cost, price, and quality of care

Authors: *Sara Jamalabadi, Vera Winter, and Jonas Schreyögg*

ABSTRACT

Objectives: Despite the widespread use of Diagnosis-Related Groups (DRGs) for hospital reimbursement, little empirical evidence exists on the effect of DRG systems on hospital behavior and, ultimately, the quality of care. Additionally, an overview on the results of prior literature is missing so far. This study aims to provide a synthesis of existing research, including an overview of the data and methods used, the quality measures, the results, as well as the strengths and weaknesses of the studies.

Methods: DRG prices can be considered to be in between individual hospital costs and external fixed prices, as they reflect the average costs of all or selected hospitals within an industry. Therefore, we included studies on hospital costs and prices, and positioned them on a continuum. In sum, 48 studies were identified and considered as high-quality studies by experts.

Results: The majority of the studies review the impact of cost on quality of care, while few studies directly focused on the impact of price. The dominant study design was based on cohort. Studies differ in measures of quality (e.g., readmissions, mortality, complications, and process) and cost/price measurement (e.g., reimbursement rate, and accounting cost). The studies exhibit large heterogeneity in populations and methodology. Although most studies did not detect a significant relationship between hospital cost and quality of care, others suggest that there is a trade-off between them. For some conditions, e.g., Acute Myocardial infraction and Pneumonia, authors rather find a trade-off while for others not. It also suggests that the relationship may depend on the condition investigated.

Conclusion: The synthesis allows to generate questions for further research as well as recommendations for the study design in researching the relationship between hospital cost, price and the quality of care. It also suggests that more research is needed to generate robust evidence on the relationship between cost, price, and quality of care. Additionally, results will inform policymakers about potentially adverse effects of price changes on hospital behavior and ultimately, the quality of care.